

Dielectric behavior of poly vinyl alcohol in presence of lithium hydroxide

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Manuscript received online 28 July 2012, revised 11 October, accepted 11 October 2013

Abstract : Extensive studies on the electrical transport properties and its related phenomena due to the transfer of lithium ion in poly vinyl alcohol (PVA) complex have been reported. The complexed PVA has gained greater attention due to considerable change in the conducting behavior of the material. In order to bring an improvement in electrical and dielectrical properties of PVA a suitable dopant; hexahydrated lithium hydroxide is added and the complex of PVA in film form has been undertaken for its dielectric investigations. In the present article study of dielectric constant, dielectric loss and loss tangent of pure PVA and lithium hydroxide doped PVA was highlighted. The dielectric behavior of the complexes at different dopant concentrations (0, 5, 10 and 30%) has been observed by measuring capacitance and dielectric loss tangent of complexed PVA films at different frequencies and temperatures.

Keywords : Poly vinyl alcohol, lithium hydroxide, dielectric constant, dielectric loss tangent, frequency.

Introduction

In the past decade the dielectric materials were utilized¹⁻⁴ mainly as circuit breakers and terminals, high frequency insulators, resistors for high voltage cables, filling compounds for transformers, spark-plugs for high compression automobiles and for special aircraft engines, air borne electronic equipments, various semiconducting rectifiers, transducers, amplifiers, resonators and memory devices. In the recent past much studies⁵⁻⁷ on dielectric properties of solids and liquids were also performed due to their matchless importance in the area of capacitor designing and microwave application with addition to light emitting devices for energy conversion to generate a wide variety of colours and variation of brightness over a very wide dynamic range. Enhanced red emission from poly vinyl alcohol with salicylic acid, *p*-phenylenediamine/polymethylmethacrylate and tertiary complex of samarium was very recently reported^{8,9}. Further, a special emphasis has been given to enhance the material properties such as chemical stability, low loss, high dielectric constant and high temperature tolerance.

The present paper is designed to get a better dielectric material. For this purpose the material employed in present

investigation, is prepared in thin film form using poly vinyl alcohol (PVA) and dopant lithium hydroxide (hexahydrated). Some dielectric properties viz. dielectric constant, dielectric loss and loss tangent of poly vinyl alcohol-lithium hydroxide system have been measured.

Experimental

First of all the solution of granular PVA (Loba Chemic, India) having nearly 1700–1800 degree of polymerization was prepared in triple deionized water at 70 °C with continuous stirring up to 4–5 h and thereafter solutions of Li(OH)₃.6H₂O (CDH, India) of different concentrations were added in PVA solution. The ratio taken for PVA and the dopant are 100 : 0, 95 : 5, 90 : 10 and 70 : 30 and were named as A, B, C and D respectively. With view to obtain the uniform sample in film form, the different mixtures were transferred into Teflon moulds. The film was dried at first in air then dried in vacuum (10⁻³ Torr). To improve the contact quality with view to getting better results, both the surfaces of film were coated¹⁰ with silver using vacuum chamber (Hindivac, vacuum pumping system model VS-A at 10⁻⁵ Torr). The dielectric properties of PVA complex were measured¹¹ by using A.C. impedance bridge [Hewlett Packard (HP), 4192 A LF

Impedance Analyser] at different frequencies and at different temperatures and determined with the help of following equation¹² :

$$\text{Dielectric constant } (E') = (C.d.)/E_0.A \quad (1)$$

where C is the capacitance, d is the film thickness and A is cross sectional area and E_0 is dielectric constant of free space.

$$\text{Dielectric loss } (E'') = E' . \tan \delta \quad (2)$$

where $\tan \delta$ is the dielectric loss tangent.

Results and discussion

The uniformly prepared film of pure PVA and its complexes with 5, 10 and 30% concentrations by wt. of $\text{Li}(\text{OH})_3$ were undertaken for the study of their dielectric properties. The results were analysed with varying the temperature, frequency and dopant concentration.

Variation of dielectric constant with temperature :

The effect of temperature on dielectric constant for all the samples has been studied at 10 kHz and shown in Fig. 1 and reported in Table 1. The point of inflection observed in each sample suggests the glass transition character of the polymeric materials. The value of dielectric

Fig. 1. Variation of dielectric constant (E') with temperature for different dopant concentrations of PVA complex at 10 kHz.

Table 1. Values of dielectric constant (E') for different PVA complexes at various temperatures and at 10 kHz frequency

Concentration	Temp. (K)				
	303	343	353	363	373
PVA : $\text{Li}(\text{OH})_3$					
100 : 0	11.77	16.71	15.22	16.01	16.28
95 : 5	10.46	24.90	23.63	26.27	24.02
90 : 10	22.28	27.40	28.33	25.60	27.09
70 : 30	28.21	54.71	61.65	66.35	63.08

constant is initially increased with increase of temperature in all the samples. From the figure it is clear that

above glass transition temperature T_g , the samples A, B and C show irregular behaviour while there is a decrease in the value of dielectric constant for sample D. At initial stage on increase of temperature, the viscosity of the complex¹³ decreases and gets acceleration in the orientation of dipoles which causes the increase of dielectric constant. Further, it has also been observed from the figure that the dielectric constant increases with increase of $\text{Li}(\text{OH})_3$ concentration. This is accounted for the creation of a large number of dipolar molecules of $\text{Li}(\text{OH})_3$ in the highly complexed PVA during the dielectric relaxation phenomenon. At higher concentration of dopant, the value of dielectric constant has been found very large but it is not much susceptible to temperature which indicates the saturation of polymeric nature of the material. This may be explained in terms of segmental motion¹⁴ of chains and cluster of PVA complex.

Variation of dielectric loss with temperature :

Fig. 2 represents the change in dielectric loss for pure PVA (A) and complexes (B, C and D) with temperature at 10 kHz which refers that the dielectric loss increases

Fig. 2. Variation of dielectric loss (E'') with temperature for various PVA complexes having different dopant concentrations at 10 kHz.

with increase of temperature as well as concentration. It is also observed that the relaxation peaks of samples A, B, C and D are slightly shifted towards right hand side with respect to one another. This explains that with increase of concentration of dopant the glass transition temperature of the PVA complexes is also increased. The enhancing efficiency of dielectric loss with higher concentration of $\text{Li}(\text{OH})_3$ is due to the generation of Li^{3+} ions, whose density affects and increases the value of A.C. conductivity and consequently the dielectric loss of the materials. The value of dielectric loss (E'') of PVA

complexes at various temperatures and at 10 kHz frequency is reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Values of $\log E''$ for different PVA complexes at various temperatures and at 10 kHz frequency

Concentration	Temp. (K)				
	303	343	353	363	373
PVA : Li(OH) ₃	303	343	353	363	373
100 : 0	0.166	0.685	0.551	0.676	0.719
95 : 5	0.202	1.285	1.243	1.410	1.388
90 : 10	1.025	1.349	1.440	1.378	1.522
70 : 30	1.076	1.871	2.013	2.116	2.095

The variation of dielectric loss tangent with temperature, frequency and concentration :

The plot of dielectric loss tangent with respect to temperature at 10 kHz for all the four samples is shown in Fig. 3. Below the glass transition temperature (T_g) it is found that the value of the $\tan \delta$ for maximum dopant

Fig. 3. Loss tangent as a function of temperature for different dopant concentrations at 10 kHz.

(30%) is very large in comparison to pure and other PVA complexes, but above T_g , the materials get soften and $\tan \delta$ value is not largely affected. This may be interpreted in terms of segmental motion of polymeric chain and cluster formation¹⁵ of Li^{3+} ion. It has also been observed that above T_g of PVA, the rate of increase of dielectric loss tangent is high. This shows the usual character of polymeric material. A dielectric relaxation curve for sample D is observed at 360 K. This peak infers the relaxation of dipolar orientation of $\text{Li}(\text{OH})_3$ molecules arised due to increase of the concentration of dopant. Fig. 4 shows the variation of $\tan \delta$ with frequency at different temperatures for 30% $\text{Li}(\text{OH})_3$ dopped polymer. The figure also explores that the dielectric loss tangent in the sample D increases with increase of tempera-

Fig. 4. Variation of loss tangent with frequency at different temperatures for 30% dopant for PVA complex.

ture. At lower frequency $\tan \delta$ is higher because low frequency at higher temperature responds large relaxation time of the dipolar molecules. The relaxation time for all the samples at 10 kHz has been found 1.6×10^{-5} s. The dielectric relaxation spectra just above glass transition temperature increases with decrease of the frequency. This may be accounted¹⁶ for an increase of mobility of charge carriers in the glass transition region and liberation of electron due to thermal heating. From Fig. 5 it is very clear that the dielectric relaxation phenomenon in polymeric complex is susceptible to the concentration of the

Fig. 5. Variation of loss tangent as a function of dopant concentration for various frequencies at room temperature.

complexing material. The quantum of variation is dependent on the magnitude and behavior of the doping material. The variation of $\tan \delta$ with concentration of lithium hydroxide at different frequencies and at room temperature has been reported in Table 3 which infers that at all the frequencies the value of $\tan \delta$ decreases with increase of the doping material. This is due to increasing dissipation factor in the system. In addition it has been found that at lower frequencies the variation in loss tangent is very high while at high frequencies it is not much affected.

Table 3. Values of $\tan \delta$ for different PVA complex at different frequency and at 298 K

Concentration PVA : Li(OH) ₃	1 kHz	10 kHz	100 kHz	500 kHz
100 : 0	1.142	0.295	0.140	0.128
95 : 5	3.210	0.978	0.363	0.234
90 : 10	3.190	0.934	0.329	0.174
70 : 30	6.690	1.971	0.684	0.359

References

1. P. Kmauth, *Solid State Ionics*, 2009, **180**, 911.
2. A. L. Polak, S. P. Weeks and J. J. Beuhler, *Sensors and Actuators*, 1986, **9**, 1.
3. J. Read, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2002, **149A**, 1190.
4. A. N. Dey, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1971, **118**, 1547.
5. A. M. Stephan and K. S. Nahm, *Polymer*, 2006, **47**, 5952.
6. A. K. Shukla and T. Pream Kumar, *Current Science*, 2008, **94**, 314.
7. Ujjal Kumar Sur, *Current Science*, 2011, **10**, 1129.
8. A. K. Singh, S. K. Singh, R. Prakash and S. B. Rai, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2010, **485**, 9.
9. G. Kaur, Y. Dwivedi and S. B. Rai, *Opt. Commun.*, 2012, **52**, 148.
10. K. P. Singh, P. N. Gupta and R. P. Singh, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1992, **19**, 31.
11. F. C. Laman, M. A. Gee and J. Denovan, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1993, **140**, 51.
12. B. Tareev, "Physics of Dielectric Materials", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1979, pp. 153-160.
13. K. C. Gong and H. S. Cai, *Mater. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.*, 1989, **136**, 377.
14. P. N. Gupta and K. P. Singh, *Solid State Ionics*, 1996, **86**, 319.
15. A. F. Basha, M. Amim, H. A. Abdel Samad and K. A. Darwish, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1988, **5**, 161.
16. R. G. Linford, "Solid State Ionic Devices", eds. B. V. R. Chowdari and S. Radhakrishna, World Scientific Press, Singapore, 1988, p. 551.